

Significance of Kāmsya Pātra : A study to revive Pākaśāstra and Assam's ethnic food Habits

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Kāmsya, কাহ or bell metal in other words an alloy of two metals namely Copper and Tin in 4:1 proportions. Bell metal craftsmanship is Assam's one of the most pertinent and unique heritage that identifies and upholds the cultural richness distinctively to the world. Over decades, numerous items of this art have acquired socio-cultural and religious significance. In other words, Assamese culture is incomplete without the utensils of the bell metal industry. From every religious rite to marriage ceremonies, the bell metal utensil carries a unique identity not only for its aristocratic golden aura but also for its benefits and functionality too. The art of Kāmsya, encompasses all sects of Hindu faiths beyond their ideological differences. May it be Nava Vaisnava sect of Srimanta Sankardeva or the Shaktism of Kamakhya Devalaya or any Buddhist worship, Kāmsya pātra is the thread of unity in diversity.

Having such a pertinent place in the culture, the craftsmanship of Kāmsya is losing its traditional importance and value in the modern advent of synthetic utensils and less costlier metals such as steel, aluminium etc. due to the ignorance on the health benefits of Kāmsya utensil and loss of sense of the idea that protection of cultural elements is preservation of one's identity.

This paper will try to evaluate the aforesaid issues from both Pākaśāstras and modern culinary sciences with the aim to protect the tradition of Kāmsya pātra, a cultural identity of Assam and Bhārat.